

Ionization

Louie R.M.B

In the last period of time, I have been doing some research on Ionization. Ionization is all about in this case, removing stuff from atoms. Atoms are made of neutrons, electrons and protons. Protons are positive, neutrons are neutral and electrons are negative. Atoms have the same number of protons and electrons. And when I said removing stuff from atoms, I meant removing electrons.

So, the way you remove electrons from atoms is by applying an X amount of energy to it.

(that's called ionization energy)

Now you might be thinking, 'what happens to an atom when you remove its electron or electrons?' Well since an atom has the same number of positive protons and negative electrons, it means that when you remove 1 electron from an atom, then you would call the atom a "Positively charged atom" Because you removed a negative electron, it now has 1 more positive proton.

(In this case X is an atom)

You might be thinking, 'Why did u write + E?'

Well because if I didn't add that how would you be able to tell if I added a proton or removed an electron? Silent now aren't you.

Now you can also do the opposite, by simply adding an electron. Then you might be able to tell that it's called a negatively charged atom, because when you make a positively charged atom you remove a negative electron so there are more positive protons, which means when you 'add' an electron then there will be more negative electrons than positive protons,

Now you might be thinking 'what's the point of ionizing an atom then?'

A great example would be 'Table salt'.

The way you make table salt is exactly by taking NA (sodium), remove an electron from the NA, then you will need CI (Chlorine), then you take an X number of electrons from the NA and add it to the CI,

That will be it for today, hope you learned a thing or two.

